

Supporting a Celtic coin die study with image matching and hierarchical clustering for creating a social networks analysis

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ABSTRACT

Studying coin dies, particularly Celtic ones, is a challenging and time-consuming task for numismatists. To support them in this task, we implemented a coin studies pipeline in ClaReNet, which we have further improved in our current DeReNum project. The aim is to maintain human involvement and oversight, which is particularly important given the challenges posed by Celtic coins for die studies, as detailed in the paper. Notably, our focus is on silver coins, which are often in worse condition than gold coins. Extremely poorly preserved coins can be eliminated by a pre-sorting step supported by the Deepcluster method. The numismatist will also be involved in this step and will have the final decision. Pre-sorting with Deepcluster is particularly useful when the number of coins is high or the state of preservation varies greatly. As a result of the pipeline, which will be explained in detail in this paper, the user will receive a dendrogram ordering the coin images (one image per coin side) and proposing clusters of coins likely to have been produced from the same die. Using the open-source tool Orange Data Mining, we also propose a way to visualise the dendrogram and provide a working environment.

Within the pipeline, we are currently comparing two image-matching algorithms: ORB and DISK. Based on tests with a dataset using a ground truth from the ClaReNet project, DISK, which is based on convolutional neural networks, performed better than ORB. However, another test showed that ORB can handle coins with different orientations more effectively.

In this paper, we will present examples of new dies identified using our pipeline. However, we are still in the early stages of the project and are currently collecting material for analysis.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Image Matching, Convolutional Neural Networks, Clustering, Celtic Coins

Introduction

In our new project, 'De Retibus Nummorum' (DeReNum)¹, we are dedicated to researching the Celtic coinage systems and the associated coins, which often feature highly abstract, ornamental patterns, using traditional numismatic and computer-assisted methods.

The objectives of our project are:

1. Reconstruction of the origin and development of the Celtic monetary economy;
2. Examination of the typological distribution and die links of selected coin series;
3. Research into the connections and dependencies in the late Celtic communication networks and economic areas.

In order to achieve these goals, we will examine selected and representative Celtic coin series from central Europe. To this end, we must first collect as many data sets as possible on these coin series from archaeological institutions and, with the appropriate permission, integrate them into the virtual union catalogue "Online Celtic Coinage"² (Wigg-Wolf et al. 2025), that was developed within the previous project ClaReNet³. A die study will then be carried out on the collected coin images, which we intend to support with algorithmic and AI-based methods such as the pipeline presented here. Traditional hand-executed die studies can take several years of work, depending on the number of coins. With our pipeline, we want to support numismatists and speed up this process. The collected data and the dies will hereafter be incorporated into a social network analysis, which can provide further insights into the trading networks of the Celts in Central Europe.

In the following, the individual data sets from the various institutions are combined into one large data set, each covering a specific series of coins, such as Bushel quinarii (Büschelquinare), the Mussel staters (Muschelstatere), or the so-called Celtic small silver. In addition to image rights, we have to deal with varying image qualities of the coin images and different types of databases. The data set of Bushel quinarii coins used in this paper currently comprises around 1,800 coins from approximately 80 different sites, mainly distributed across southern Germany, Austria, Switzerland, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia. The coins were minted between approximately 150 and 25 BC and feature the eponymous Bushels on the front, and a stylised horse in motion on the back (Fig. 1 right).

Figure 1 – Two coins with obverse and reverse from our dataset. The coin on the left still shows a clearly recognisable head and belongs to the prototype in Allen's typology. The coin on the right has been classified as type E and shows the already very abstract Bushels. Both coins show a horse with additional markings on the reverse. (Photos left: St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC no. 2467; Photos right: C. von Nicolai, Staatliche Münzsammlung München OCC no. 3095)

They weigh approximately 1.2 to 1.8 g, and have a diameter of about 12 mm. The coins are either silver coins or coins that appear to be silver, being plated, which means they have an iron or copper core. The silver content is then concentrated only on the visible surface. One particular challenge posed by these coins is the development of the image on the obverse, which is believed

¹ DeReNum project blog: <https://derenum.hypotheses.org/>.

² Online Celtic Coinage catalogue: <https://occ.dainst.org/>.

³ ClaReNet project blog: <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/>.

by researchers to have evolved from a head in profile to a highly abstract representation of various articulated Bushels (Fig. 1). This is reflected above all in the five different typologies, which contain varying numbers of subtypes and associated datings. We currently use Derek F. Allen's typology (Allen 1978), because other typologies are based on it and can be subordinated to it, whereas the other typologies ((Kellner 1990, Ziegauß 2000, Brandt & Irlinger 2002; Nick 2012) are not compatible with each other. Due to the typical characteristics of archaeological material, this classification naturally does not result in subtypes of equal size in terms of the number of coins. However, since we do not want to train a classification model at this stage, an underrepresentation of some types is currently not problematic (c.f. Gampe & Tolle 2024). In addition, these coins also present other challenges, such as varying degrees of preservation and restoration, as well as incomplete die impressions on many coins. Since these partial impressions are a common feature of Celtic coins, and were caused not only by die slipping but also by blanks that were too small for the die. This incompleteness did not seem to be a reason for the mint masters at the time not to put these coins into circulation. Nonetheless, these factors not only make it difficult for numismatists to find die links, but also for our coin die pipeline to deal with. However, even poorly preserved coins are relevant to our project, as we need a data set as large as possible to test our tools and approaches.

Related Work

In recent years, automated ancient coin die studies have been developed for various coin series. So far, Greek and Roman coins in particular have received the most attention. This was made possible by keypoint-based image matching technology, which allowed coin images to be compared with each other based on specific characteristics, known as keypoints. This technology was developed at the end of the last millennium by D. G. Lowe, who designed the SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform: Lowe 1999) algorithm. These algorithmic methods were the standard in image matching for a long time, and have been further developed over the years by approaches such as SURF (Speeded Up Robust Features: Bay & Van Gool 2006) and ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF: Rublee et al. 2011). In recent years, machine learning methods have also been incorporated to further increase the performance of these matchers. Deep learning approaches such as convolutional neural networks (DISK: Tyszkiewicz et al. 2020) and transformer models (SuperGlue: Sarlin et al. 2019) are used here.

Automated die studies on ancient coins have not yet been attempted on a large scale. The CADS approach (Computer-Aided Die Study) was the first attempt in 2020 to support numismatists in this challenging work (Taylor 2020). The pipeline was very similar to ours, as it used ORB and hierarchical clustering. However, this approach was developed and tested on very well-preserved Greek coins. A year later, Heinecke et al. published a study that used a similar system with Gaussian Process (GP) keypoints and Bayesian microclustering on Neronian silver denarii (Heinecke et al. 2021). In 2024, an approach was developed using a deep learning-based XFeat model for keypoint detection and subsequent clustering with the label propagation clustering method (Cornet et al. 2024). This approach was also tested on Greek coins.

A new study was recently published that also uses a keypoint system to create an overlay from two coins and then uses an SSIM score (Structural Similarity) to find similarities on both surfaces (Labedan et al. 2025). The numismatic basis for this study was a hoard of Roman coins. It is therefore clear that keypoint-based image matching is not a new approach for ancient coins. However, the mentioned studies cover well preserved Greek and Roman coins. Celtic coins, which differ significantly in design from Greek and Roman coins often possess incomplete impressions, thus posing a completely different challenge, were not tested. Therefore, our pipeline focuses on the numismatic legacy of the Celts.

Deepcluster for pre-sorting

The first step in our pipeline consists of pre-sorting the coin images using the unsupervised Deepcluster approach (Caron et al. 2019). As we had already had good experiences with Deepcluster for pre-sorting coin images in the ClaReNet project, it made sense to use it again

(Deligio et al. 2024). We would like to remove severely damaged coins whose images are heavily worn or corroded from the dataset, as we want to increase the chance of linking very similar coins with each other in the subsequent pipeline steps. However, we want to proceed carefully so that we do not remove too many coins in our already limited data set.

Figure 2 - Sections from two clusters after applying Decluster. The upper cluster contains better-preserved coins of various types, while the lower cluster consists of coins that are difficult to identify. (Photos top: N.N., Archäologisches Museum Kehlheim OCC No.2267; St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC nos. 2409, 2412, 2462, 2463, 2502, 2508, 2654; C. von Nicolai, Stadtarchiv Ingolstadt OCC nos. 2766, 2768, 2789, 2228, 2849, 2852, 2864, 2882, 2920, 2927. Photos bottom: St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC nos. 2510, 2550, 2555, 2563, 2564, 2566, 2579, 2590, 2592, 2597, 2617, 2632, 2657, 2686, 2710, 2722; C. von Nicolai, Stadtarchiv Ingolstadt OCC no. 2862)

The Deepcluster model uses components of a convolutional neural network (CNN) to extract features from the coin images in the first step. This creates a feature vector for each image in the dataset. These are then clustered using a k-means algorithm. The individual clusters are subsequently given a pseudo label, which is used in the next step as a class for training the CNN.

This improves the selection of important features and the classification of clusters with each step of the training (Caron et al. 2019).

We applied Deepcluster separately to the front and back of our Bushel series data set of 1.800 coins. The number of clusters (k) was set in advance at 45 for the obverses and 40 for the reverses. This ensured that the number of images in the cluster did not become too large or too small. Deepcluster itself attempts to make the clusters the same size anyway. Due to this behaviour and the fact that the clusters have to be evaluated manually after the run, it is not necessary to find an optimal number for k. The training was carried out with a learning rate of 0.05, a batch size of 128, and a duration of 200 epochs for both sides. As a result, we obtained many coin image clusters whose surface had a very similar appearance. However, it contained many coins of different subtypes of the Allen typology, both on the obverse and reverse sides. (Fig. 2 top).

After manually reviewing the entire result, we were also able to identify clusters that contained only coins in very poor condition (Fig. 2 below). This meant that a total of 129 coin obverse images from five clusters and 97 reverse images from four clusters could be removed from the dataset. Searching for poorly preserved coins in very large sets of images with very different looking coins would have made this very tiring for the eyes, and therefore also much more time-consuming.

Coin die studies pipeline

Our coin die studies pipeline is designed to make it easier for numismatists to find dies in a large dataset of coin images. This means the domain expert would remain in the loop to finally decide. We do not envision generating a 100% automatic approach. In ancient times, coins were produced using two dies, the upper one (reverse) being movable and the lower one (obverse) fixed. This meant that the upper die wore out faster than the lower one, and had to be replaced after a certain number of minting operations. Thus, the lower die could have been used with two or more upper dies. This resulted in die links, which can be reconstructed from the coins found. Reconstructing and understanding these connections enables numismatists to establish a relative chronology for a coin series - a die study. Since there are generally no written sources in prehistoric archaeology, this is often the only way to date celtic coins. To do this, however, one first has to identify the dies themselves. This can be a very time-consuming task, as a large number of coins must be compared with each other in terms of their similarity and, above all, the details of the coin image. To speed up this process, our idea for the ClaReNet project was to use keypoint extraction and image matching algorithms that are capable of evaluating the similarity of coin images. At that time, we tested the approaches already available for finding coin dies, which also worked with image matching. However, these methods had only been tested on Roman and Greek coins. Our Celtic coins differ from these in that their motifs often appear very abstract and frequently lack legends. After several tests failed to produce promising results, we decided to develop our own pipeline.

There are currently two different versions of our pipeline, which differ in terms of the image matching algorithms used (ORB or DISK). Both versions share the following basic structure (Fig. 3):

Preprocessing the images

First, a five-step preprocessing is applied to the coin images: This involves (1) removing the colour from the image (Gray scaling), (2) improving the contrast (Histogram equalization), (3) reducing the image sharpness (Denoise), (4) improving the contrast again (Histogram equalization) and, finally, (5) removing as much of the coin's edge as possible (Circle crop). This serves to minimise bias as far as possible. The bias primarily involves components of the coin, such as corrosion or abrasion damage, and the coin edge, which can distract the image-matching algorithm from the actual coin image. The differences in the lighting of the coin images, some of which were provided to us by various institutions, should also be minimised here.

Figure 3 – Schematic representation of both coin die studies pipelines. (Graph: S. Gampe, Big Data Lab, Photos top: N.N. Staatliche Münzsammlung München OCC no. 3095; C. von Nicolai, Deggendorf Kreisarchäologie OCC no. 3372. Orange images: Orange Data Mining. Coin photos top cluster: C. von Nicolai, Stadtarchiv Ingolstadt OCC no. 2923, 2884; St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC nos. 2424, 2418, 2450, 2456; C. von Nicolai, Staatliche Münzsammlung München OCC no. 2975. Coin photos bottom cluster: N.N., Salzburg Museum OCC no. 3161; St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC nos. 3602, 2468, 3679; N.N, Landesmuseum Württemberg Stuttgart OCC no. 2277; C. von Nicolai, Stadtmuseum Ingolstadt OCC no. 3502)

Keypoint extraction and matching

The image matching algorithm then attempts to extract keypoints on each image in the data set. These are special features of the coin, such as edges or lines on the coin relief. The keypoints are stored as a set so that they are available again in the next step. The key points of two images are then compared in pairs. Each key point and its immediate surroundings are examined for similarities with the key points and their surroundings on other coins. As soon as the algorithm identifies two key points as a match, this is stored. When such matches for two coin images are visualised, the key points are represented by lines connecting them (Fig. 3). These lines should be as horizontal as possible, as only keypoints in the same regions of the coins should be made when the coin image is aligned in the same way. Finally, the matches found for a coin pair are counted and entered into a table with $n \times n$ (n = number of coins in the data set) fields. In the end, this table contains the number of matches for each coin pair in the data set. Each row of this table shows the similarity of one coin to all other coins in the data set. Mathematically speaking, such a row forms a vector and can therefore be easily compared with the other vectors in the table.

Hierarchical clustering

In the penultimate step, the distances between all vectors in the table are calculated using the summed differences for each pair of vectors and the results are stored in a new table. In the final step, the distance table is the base for using an agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm. First, all coin vectors are treated as individual clusters. Then, the two vectors closest to each other are iteratively merged into a new cluster. The distance table for the new cluster is then updated. There are various ways of calculating distance in this clustering (complete, single, average, weighted, and Ward). Within the Orange Datamining tool, the user (the domain expert) is also free to switch between them in order to experiment and see their effect on the results. The merging is repeated until all coin vectors are combined into a single cluster. The result of this process is ultimately presented in a dendrogram. This is a tree structure that organises all data points hierarchically and can thus represent the sequence of cluster mergers through its subtrees. Each subtree symbolises the merger of two or more coins into a new cluster. The closer the individual coin images are connected to each other through the tree structure, the more similar the coins depicted should be and the higher the chance that these coins were produced from the same die. The tree structure should therefore help the numismatists to find new dies in our data set.

Differences in ORB and DISK image matching algorithms

Both versions of the pipeline differ in terms of the algorithms used for image matching. The first version from the ClaReNet project (Deligio et al. 2024) uses the ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF: Rublee et. al. 2011) algorithm, while the second variant, developed by Markus Fiedler in his master's thesis (Fiedler 2025), uses the DISK (Discrete Keypoints: Tyszkiewicz et al. 2020) algorithm. For both variants, we use standardised preprocessing which was already described (s.a.) (Fig. 3)⁴.

ORB and DISK differ in the way key points are detected in an image. ORB uses a purely algorithmic approach and primarily searches for noticeable contrast changes and visible corners. The FAST (Features from Accelerated Segment Test) detector is used for this purpose, which considers a circle of surrounding pixels with a radius of 3 pixels (Bresenham-circle) for each point in the image. This means that these 16 pixels are checked to see whether they are brighter or darker than the centre pixel. If a threshold value (usually 12 pixels) is exceeded, the point is recognised as a corner, for example (Rublee et. al. 2011). DISK, on the other hand, looks for specific structures or patterns in the image. It uses convolutional neural networks (CNN) from the field of machine learning and can therefore also detect key points in areas of an image with smoother transitions which are therefore less visually striking in geometric terms. A CNN pre-

⁴ The first version of the pipeline originally also had a five-step preprocessing with a different algorithm (total variation regularisation). However, for better comparability, we decided to only use the variant from Fiedler 2025.

trained on a large image dataset is used for this purpose. Here, local features are extracted from the image by several convolutional layers and stored as feature maps. These are passed on to the next layer in reduced resolution (pooling). After the last convolution layer, a score is now calculated for each point on the feature map, indicating the probability of a keypoint being present. If a threshold value is exceeded, a keypoint is then output (Tyszkiewicz et al. 2020).

The description of keypoints and their comparison in two different images also differs between the two algorithms. ORB uses BRIEF (Binary Robust Independent Elementary Features) descriptors, which construct a binary string by comparing the brightness of several pixel pairs in an area around the keypoint. These binary chains are then compared when matching two keypoints on different images. The Hamming distance, which counts the number of different positions in the chains, is used for this purpose. The smaller this sum is, the greater the similarity between two keypoints is (Rublee et. al. 2011). DISK uses a feature vector, which is created at the end of the convolutional layers, to describe the keypoints. These vectors, which describe points in high-dimensional space, are then compared for two keypoints on different image pairs using Euclidean distance. The smaller the distance between two keypoints, the more likely it is that they are a match. At the end of the matching process for two images, the paired keypoints are recorded. While ORB simply counts the number of matches, DISK's score is based on the quality of the matches rather than their number (Tyszkiewicz et al. 2020).

Transfer to Orange Data Mining

The table as a csv file with the numbers or matching scores is then loaded into the Orange Data Mining app⁵. There, widgets with various functions are assembled into a workflow. This workflow looks like this for our coin images: First, the csv file is loaded into the programme and then displayed as a table. In the following, the paths to the image folders can be adjusted if they differ from the paths in the csv file. The table can then be displayed again for checking. Now the features from the table are selected for distance calculation in the next widget. Due to testing and the different ways in which the matching scores are specified by both algorithms, the Pearson distance metric is used for ORB and the Spearman distance metric for DISK (Fiedler 2025). After the calculation, hierarchical clustering is performed and you can now view and select the different subtrees in this widget. The coins from these selected subtrees are then displayed in the last widget. These last two widgets are used by our numismatists to locate the dies. It was therefore necessary to briefly instruct them in how to use this workflow.

Implementation and metrics

Both pipelines were implemented using Jupyter Notebook, Python and Orange Data Mining. The first pipeline uses OpenCV's ORB algorithm⁶, while the second pipeline uses Kornia's DISK implementation⁷. The running times are as follows: Preprocessing the second pipeline takes just a few minutes. This represents a significant improvement compared to the first pipeline, where this process took several hours. Keypoint detection and matching take about eight hours for our dataset of approximately 1,560 (after Deepcluster pre-sorting) images (both sides of the coins) with a nVidia RTX 3090 GPU. This is mainly due to the fact that both ORB and DISK have to compare the keypoints of each image with every other image in the dataset during the matching step. In the worst case, this results in an asymptotic quadratic runtime ($O(n^2)$). However, optimisations in the respective algorithms help to reduce this runtime. In contrast, distance calculation and hierarchical clustering in Orange are performed in a few seconds for our data set.

In his master's thesis, M. Fiedler was able to show that the second version of the pipeline, using the DISK algorithm, was able to improve performance on a dataset from the ClaReNet project (Tab. 1). For this dataset of Corosolitae staters from the hoard of Le Catillon II, there is a die study by Philip de Jersey with approximately 1,300 coins. In the first version of the pipeline, the number

⁵ Orange Data Mining: <https://orangedatamining.com/>.

⁶ OpenCV's documentation of ORB: https://docs.opencv.org/3.4/d1/d89/tutorial_py_orb.html.

⁷ Kornia's documentation of DISK: <https://kornia.readthedocs.io/en/latest/feature.html#kornia.feature.DISK>.

of clusters generated that contained at least 70% coins with the same die was counted. A total of 208 such clusters were found (Deligio et al. 2024). The second version of the pipeline increased this number to 226. If the proportion of coins with the same die is increased to 100% per cluster, then the DISK pipeline not only created 26 new clusters, but also more than doubled the number of coins contained in the clusters (Fiedler 2025).

Table 1 – Number of clusters and coins contained in the respective clusters (#) for 70% and 100% consistency (belonging to the same die).

Method	70% - number of clusters	# 70% - number of coins	100% – number of clusters	# 100% - number of coins
ORB (Deligio et al. 2024)	208	-	194	489
DISK (Fiedler 2025)	226	1175	219	1078

Summary

Due to these significantly better results, we decided to primarily use only the second pipeline and to use the ORB pipeline only for comparisons. However, during an experiment with the DISK pipeline, we discovered a problem with rotation invariance. ORB is claimed to be rotation invariant (Ruble et al. 2011) while DISK is claimed to be very robust against rotations (Tyszkiewicz et al. 2020). In an experiment with golden mussle staters from Manching (Ziegeus 2013), we rotated each of these coins in five-degree increments until a full rotation was achieved. These 72 new images were used together with 286 other mussle staters as input for both pipelines. After running both pipelines, the result was surprising. While the ORB pipeline placed all images of the rotated coin in pairs in a subtree and then combined these subtrees into larger subtrees consisting only of these coin images, this was not the case with the DISK pipeline. Although some coins were also linked in pairs at the lowest levels of the dendrogram, a total of eleven merges of subtrees were required before all rotated coins were in one cluster. However, this cluster then also includes all coin images from the rest of the data set. With the ORB pipeline, only six subtree levels were needed to merge all rotated images in the dendrogram, whereby this cluster then also consists only of these images. This clearly shows that the ORB algorithm can handle rotated coin images much better than DISK. However, since DISK performed better on the dataset with the Coriolitae staters and the problem with rotated coins is rather negligible due to the manual alignment of all images in our datasets, we will continue to use the DISK pipeline primarily in our project. The experiment shows that even newer approaches, which appear to offer better performance, cannot always handle all eventualities in archaeological material. Despite variations in the orientation or lighting of our coin images, we were able to successfully apply our pipeline and identify new coin dies. We are currently planning to have an evaluation of the two image matching algorithms carried out as part of a student's master thesis. The aim will be to find out in which cases it is better to use one algorithm and when the other, in order to optimise our results with regard to the die study. In addition, tests will be carried out to determine whether the two algorithms can be combined in a meaningful way.

Preliminary results

As we are still in the early stages of the project, we would like to show only a few preliminary results of the pre-sorting with Deepcluster and the coin die study pipeline here. In our opinion, pre-sorting with Deepcluster was successful, as over 200 images with coins in very poor condition could be sorted out with manageable effort. The most time-consuming task here was running the Deepcluster algorithm, which took about two hours for each side of the Bushel quinar data set. For verification purposes, the coins already sorted out with Deepcluster were used once again as input for our coin studies pipeline, together with the rest of the data set. We found that the sorted-out coins were very often contained in a subtree with the better-preserved coins. However, due to their

poor condition, it is not really possible to determine that they originate from the same die. There were also very few subtrees that consisted predominantly of these poorly preserved coins and could therefore have been neglected in the evaluation. This test then confirmed our assessment that sorting out items, which could also have been done manually but would have taken considerably more time, did not have a negative impact on the result.

The numismatic assessment of the subtrees of our coin studies pipeline, on the other hand, is still a work in progress. However, some coins with identical dies have already been discovered by our numismatists with the help of the dendrogram generated by hierarchical clustering. The dendrogram forms a tree structure that allows numismatists themselves to select a fitting cluster size by clicking on a subtree. As examples, here are two coins from a obverse cluster and four coins from a reverse cluster, which we believe were each produced with the same die (Fig. 4).

Figure 4 – Examples of coins struck with the same die (boxed in red) from the dendrogram in the Orange Data Mining app. Top: obverses, below: reverses. (Photos top: C. von Nicolai, Gäuboudenmuseum Straubing OCC no. 2222; St. Friedrich, Archäologische Staatssammlung München OCC nos. 2480, 2411; C. von Nicolai, Deggendorf Kreisarchäologie OCC nos. 3400, 3372, 3451. Photos bottom: C. von Nicolai, Deggendorf Kreisarchäologie OCC nos. 3365, 3454, 3406, 3367, 3381, 3463, 3436, 3450. 3410)

In a one-hour experiment, the numismatist was able to assign 61 coins to seven different dies, based on the 3069 coin images (1547 obverse and 1522 reverse images) in Orange that remained after the pre-sorting. It must be noted that coins from the same die in our experiment not always appeared directly next to each other. Nevertheless, it saved a great deal of time to find some coins from the same die in subtrees next to each other.

On the cluster with the obverse sides, we paid particular attention to the dots in the centre, which are typical for the Allen type E, and to the position and size of the Bushels during the evaluation (Fig. 4 top). On the reverse side, the position of the horse's legs is particularly useful for comparison. In the example shown here, the additional points in the upper half of the coin image must also be taken into account (Fig 4 bottom). These examples show two clusters with very similar coins, where the probability of finding coins with the same die is high. However, not all of our subtrees in the entire dendrogram of our more than 1,500 coins look this uniform. There are also many subtrees that contain coins that look very different at first glance. This can also be seen quickly when going through the clusters by looking at the Allen type that we have added to the end of the file name of the coin images. However, our numismatists do not rule out the possibility that we may also find coins of the same die (at least for one side) among coins of different types.

Furthermore, due to the very large dendrogram with over 1,500 coins, we have independently adapted the OrangeWidget for hierarchical clustering. It has proven to be very tedious to search for specific images in the dendrogram using the file name, as there is no search field for this purpose. We have therefore added two input fields for marking file names, which accept either series of numbers or numbers combined with letters as input. All file names that match the information in the input fields are now highlighted in colour, significantly speeding up the search and thus also the evaluation of the dendrogram for numismatists.

Overall, however, it should be noted that the task of conducting a die study on our Celtic Bushel coins remains challenging, even with the help of our new pipeline. Nevertheless, we hope to be able to significantly accelerate the task in this way in the near future.

Summary and conclusion

Despite their large distribution over Central Europe, the Celtic coins of the Bushel series have only been preserved in relatively small numbers, compared to other coin series, and thus represent a challenging subject of study for our DeReNum project. This is mainly due to the motifs on their obverse sides, which changed over the course of their production period from a clearly recognisable representation of a head to very abstract bushels/tufts, which has already inspired several researchers to develop different typologies. For our project, however, the most important thing is to find coin dies for both sides of the coin. This time-consuming work is normally carried out manually by numismatists.

To speed up this research, we have already developed a coin studies pipeline based on the ORB algorithm in the ClaReNet project. This pipeline was further developed by M. Fiedler based on the DISK algorithm, which uses a convolutional neural network to find keypoints, and we used it in our project on our Bushel series dataset of approx. 1,800 coins. Before applying the new pipeline, we used the unsupervised Deecluster model to sort out images of severely damaged coins whose surfaces were barely recognisable.

Our coin studies pipeline itself is available in two versions, which share the same basic structure but differ in the image matching algorithms used (ORB and DISK). As described above, the pipeline starts with preprocessing and applying the matching algorithms. The results are then used within Orange Datamining where a hierarchical clustering is performed. The resulting dendrogram is visualized in Orange and can be used by the domain experts. They can interactively clicking on the clusters in the dendrogram and look at the corresponding images of the coins. By adopting the widgets in Orange, the domain experts can assign dies to coins if they want to.

ORB and DISK differ primarily in the way keypoints are detected in images. While ORB uses a purely algorithmic approach and searches for corners and areas with high contrast, DISK uses a convolutional neural network to look for striking structures and patterns. DISK delivered better

results on a ground truth dataset from the ClaReNet project. However, an experiment with rotated coins showed that ORB is significantly more robust when dealing with rotated images. We therefore intend to conduct a further evaluation of the respective strengths and weaknesses of the individual algorithms. With the DISK Pipeline, we have already been able to find several dies in the Bushel series data set. We intend to intensify this evaluation in the near future.

Currently, there is no version of the pipeline with an easy-to-install app. Due to the costs involved (GPU support recommended), we are also unable to host the pipeline ourselves. If you want to use the pipeline, you will need to install the image matching software from GitHub (or Zenodo) with the necessary components yourself. The Orange Data Mining app, on the other hand, can be downloaded and installed as a package and can then be used even by non-IT experts. Once the installation hurdle has been overcome, other case studies (not limited to coins) can also be carried out without major code adjustments, as the algorithms used do not only work on Celtic coins.

The next steps in the DeReNum project will involve evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of the two image matching algorithms. The aim is to identify cases in which one or the other algorithm offers advantages. In addition, we would like to evaluate the matching itself with the visualisation of keypoint matches for very similar and very different coins.

If we find enough dies in our data sets (not limited to the Bushel series) during the course of the project, we would like to compile a new data set that contains our dies as ground truth and is therefore also suitable for training machine learning models. This will be used to test various CNN and/or transformer-based models.

In addition, we would like to conduct a social network analysis (SNA), a method used in the social sciences. The archaeological sites will serve as nodes in such a network. Edges are then created between these nodes if both locations yield either coins of the same die or of the same type. The aim is to gain further insights into Celtic trade networks in our area. These results will also be illustrated with maps based on GIS.

Both the machine learning and SNA approaches were tested by computer science students as part of the 'Data Challenges' course in the summer semester of 2025, yielding some interesting results for us. These student projects still need to be evaluated further by our project team and can then be incorporated into our further research.

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

The coin die study pipeline (DISK) developed by Markus Fiedler is available on GitHub: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19662346>

The coin die study pipeline from the ClaReNet project (ORB) is available on GitHub: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19631107>

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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